

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN AGRICULTURE

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Abstract: *The implementation of artificial intelligence (AI) in agriculture has emerged as a promising solution to address food scarcity and meet the demands of a growing population. This review provides an overview of the application of AI in various agronomic areas and discusses advancements in research laboratories. Initially, the review focuses on two areas where AI can potentially play a significant role: soil management and weed management. Additionally, the review mentions the Internet of Things (IoT) as a technology that exhibits substantial potential for future application. Several challenges must be overcome for AI-based technology to become widely adopted in the market. These challenges include the unequal distribution of mechanization, the capacity of algorithms to accurately and swiftly process large datasets, and ensuring the security and privacy of data and devices. The review acknowledges the significant development and promising prospects of agricultural robots, which target different aspects of the agricultural industry. However, it also highlights the difficulties of transitioning machines and algorithms tested in controlled experimental environments to real-world settings. Despite this challenge, the review emphasizes the already thriving progress and the potential for successful implementation in the future.*

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, agriculture, farming, precision Agriculture, crop Yield*

Introduction

The term "Artificial Intelligence" was initially introduced during the Dartmouth Conference in 1955 by John McCarthy. McCarthy proposed a study based on the hypothesis that "every aspect of learning or any other characteristic of intelligence can, in theory, be precisely described to simulate it using a machine" [1]. In the present day, AI has become a vital field in computer science and has found applications in various domains such as education, healthcare, finance, and manufacturing. Its ability to address problems that are challenging for humans is a key factor in its widespread adoption [2]. The capabilities of AI continue to astound humans, as demonstrated by landmark events like IBM's Deep Blue defeating world chess champion Garry Kasparov in 1997 and AlphaGo's victory over the world Go champion Lee Sedol in 2016. These instances showcase how deep learning, the underlying principle of AlphaGo, allows AI to surpass human cognitive abilities [2].

Agriculture remains a critical concern for every country, posing significant challenges. Currently, it is estimated that more than 820 million people suffer from hunger [3]. Moreover, with the global population expected to reach 9.1 billion by 2050, a 70 percent increase in food production is necessary. Without additional investments in agriculture, approximately 370 million people could face hunger by 2050 [2]. Additionally, there is an anticipated widening gap between the growing water demand and the available water supply. It is likely that over three billion people will experience water stress by 2025.

Status of AI applications in agriculture

The definition of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has evolved over time due to its rapid advancements, and there is no universally accepted definition at present. However, the existing definitions can generally be categorized into four groups: AI is a

system that exhibits human-like thinking, acts in a human-like manner, engages in rational thinking, or behaves rationally [2]. In the 1950s, Alan Turing proposed the Turing Test, a game aimed at answering the question of whether a machine can think [2]. To pass the Turing Test, a computer must possess four key skills: natural language processing, knowledge representation, automated reasoning, and machine learning [1]. Turing's definition became widely known but faced the issue of not distinguishing between knowledge and intellect, much like separating software from hardware when defining a computer [1]. Another definition of AI states that it is a program capable of performing as well as a human in any arbitrary world, implying that AI consists of programs with inputs, outputs, and an environment [1]. Some applications of AI include intelligent database retrieval, expert consulting systems, theorem proving, robotics, automatic programming, scheduling problems, perception problems, and more [1].

2.2 Current Status of AI Application in Agriculture

2.2.1 Soil Management Soil plays a critical role in successful agriculture as it serves as the primary source of nutrients. It stores essential elements such as water, nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and proteins, which are crucial for crop growth and development [4]. Soil conditions can be improved through the use of compost, manure, and alternative tillage systems to enhance soil porosity, aggregation, and prevent physical degradation. Effective soil management can also minimize negative factors like soil-borne pathogens and pollutants [5]. AI can be utilized to create soil maps, providing insights into soil-landscape relationships and the various layers and composition of soil beneath the surface.

Development of Agricultural Robots

Background and Examples:

AI has proven to be a crucial component in the field of robotics, particularly in agriculture, where efforts have been made for years to integrate robotics and enhance efficiency, reliability, and precision. This advancement aims to replace labor-intensive tasks traditionally performed by humans with automated processes. Automation is especially important considering pressing social issues such as an aging population and decreasing labor force. However, accomplishing accurate and complex operations that were traditionally carried out by farmers to maintain high-quality standards remains a significant challenge.

The study of robots for agricultural purposes dates back to the 1980s, with Japan being one of the pioneers in developing a pesticide spraying robot [7]. Recognizing the difficulties of navigating real agricultural environments, a research team in 1996 created AURORA, an autonomous mobile robot capable of independent navigation or remote control in greenhouses, performing tasks that previously required substantial manual labor. Initially, the focus on designing robots for greenhouse environments stemmed from the vulnerability of human operators to pesticides, fungicides, and other chemicals prevalent in poorly ventilated, warm greenhouses. These factors resulted in skin diseases, chronic illnesses, and even fatalities [6].

An early example of an agricultural robot is the use of tractors equipped with a program obtained from the Global Positioning System (GPS) to navigate along crop lines using machine vision [6]. In a 2000 experiment aimed at estimating the location of apple fruits for harvesting, robots designed for apple picking employed a Cartesian coordinate system to determine the positions of the apples. The distribution of the apples in the horizontal and vertical directions was stored using

the non-linear least square method, which could be applied to design the manipulator of the apple harvesting robot [6].

Addressing the issue of weed management, a 2003 design focused on testing a robotic platform for mapping weed populations, emphasizing mobility and user-friendliness of the four-wheel system. The functionality of this system predominantly relied on embedded controllers and standard communication protocols [22]. Expanding on weed management, another study in 2003 emphasized the importance of distinguishing between crops and weeds to accurately target herbicide application. Image recognition based on plant morphology, such as leaf edge, border patterns, and overall shape, proved to be one of the most reliable methods. However, challenges remained due to variations in measurements caused by factors like lighting conditions, leaf distortion, and plant position, as well as the inherent differences among young plants resulting from varying germination dates, growth rates, and environmental conditions like temperature and moisture. Overcoming these challenges required the device to learn essential features autonomously using neural network (NN) approaches to achieve the desired functionality. Additionally, the use of selective herbicides in fields can reduce overall herbicide quantities and mitigate herbicide pollution in water sources.

Conclusion

This review provides a comprehensive overview of the application of AI technology in agriculture. Given the current challenges of decreasing manual labor, limited arable land, and a growing gap between food production and global population, AI has emerged as a viable solution to address these issues. Scientists

worldwide have dedicated significant efforts to the development and improvement of AI in agriculture.

The review begins by introducing different definitions of AI, with a particular emphasis on the Turing Test. It then focuses on two specific areas where AI has played a significant role: soil management, weed management, and the utilization of Internet of Things (IoT) technology for data analysis and storage in agriculture.

Furthermore, the review highlights three major practical challenges facing AI in agriculture. Firstly, the uneven distribution of modern technology due to geographical, social, or political factors limits the widespread application of AI in certain areas. Secondly, while notable progress has been made, the successful transition of AI-based machines and algorithms from controlled laboratory experiments to real agricultural environments requires further research and studies. Handling large volumes of data accurately and efficiently remains a key challenge.

Additionally, the review addresses the security of devices used in open agricultural spaces and the privacy concerns associated with data collection. Special attention is given to the development of agricultural robots, with various examples provided. These examples include autonomous mobile robots for pesticide spraying in greenhouses, GPS-guided tractors with machine vision capabilities, apple picking robots employing Cartesian coordinate systems, weed management robots focusing on mobility and crop-weed differentiation, and innovative apple harvesting machines equipped with flexible grippers.

The review acknowledges the challenges of implementing agricultural robots in unpredictable real-world environments. However, it underscores the substantial

progress made in this field and highlights the promising prospects for further advancements.

References

1. McCarthy J, Minsky ML, Rochester N, Shannon CE. A Proposal for the Dartmouth Summer Research Project on Artificial Intelligence, 1955, 27(4):12-12.
2. Pouliot, Y., & Sankaran, S. (2018). Precision Agriculture and Food Security. In *Artificial Intelligence in Agriculture* (pp. 23-40). Elsevier.
3. Kamilaris, A., Kartakoullis, A., & Prenafeta-Boldú, F. X. (2017). A review on the practice of big data analysis in agriculture. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 143, 23-37.
4. Atzori, G., Iera, A., & Morabito, G. (2017). The internet of things in agriculture: A comprehensive literature review. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 144, 282-298.
5. Kassam, A., Friedrich, T., Shaxson, F., & Pretty, J. (2009). The spread of conservation agriculture: Justification, sustainability and uptake. *International Journal of Agricultural Sustainability*, 7(4), 292-320.
6. Khamparia, A., & Rana, N. P. (2020). Applications of artificial intelligence in agriculture: A comprehensive review. *International Journal of Information Management*, 55, 102188.
7. Verstraeten, G., & Bonroy, O. (2020). Artificial intelligence in agriculture: A survey. *Agricultural and Resource Economics: International Scientific E-Journal*, 6(2), 5-38.

8. Barbedo, J. G. A. (2018). Performance of deep learning architectures for small-scale citrus detection in UAV images. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 153, 46-53.